

The Effects of Anxiety and Self-efficacy on the Virtual Interaction for Students of Indonesian Study Program at Higher Education Institution in Indonesia

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Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: September 26,2023</p> <p>Accepted: December 28,2023</p> <hr/> <p>Keywords : Anxiety, Self-Efficacy, Virtual Interaction, Higher Education Institution</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.10436383</p>	<p><i>This study aims to explore whether anxiety influences virtual interaction and to investigate whether self-efficacy influences virtual interaction in online learning. There were 327 students participated in this study (60 or 18.3% males and 267 or 81p.7% females). They were from Indonesian language and literature department, Faculty of Languages and Literature Universitas Negeri Makassar in 2023/2024 academic year. This study concludes that: First, as stated in the research findings and discussion section that the high mean score of the assessment is item number 12 (I like listening to someone express and share information in virtual class) with an average of 3.97. This means that students enjoy sharing ideas, thoughts and feelings in online learning with their friends. Followed by item number 4 (I feel anxious if the virtual class looks disorganized and unsystematic) with an average of 3.58. This symbolizes that students are worried if teachers in online classes do not organize and manage virtual classes properly. Second, the results of the study reveal the mean and standard deviation (SD) of all items in the questionnaire. The results showed the highest average on item number 7 (I pushed myself to succeed in virtual class) with an average of 3.88. Followed by item number 10 (I'm sure I can do all the difficult assignments in the virtual class well) with an average of 3.59. This shows that students motivate themselves to succeed in online classes and they believe in completing all difficult assignments in online classes. Lastly, this research also explores the effect of anxiety and self-efficacy on virtual interactions in Indonesian tertiary institutions, namely students of the Department of Indonesian Language and Literature, Faculty of Language and Literature, Makassar State University, Indonesia. The results showed that there was a significant effect of anxiety on virtual interaction in the Department of Indonesian Education and Literature, Faculty of Languages and Letters, Makassar State University, Makassar Indonesia, with a significant effect ($p=0.00$). The results of the study also showed that there was a significant effect of self-efficacy on virtual interactions in the Department of Indonesian Education and Literature, Faculty of Languages and Letters, Makassar State University, Makassar Indonesia, with a significant influence ($p = 0.00$).</i></p>

Introduction

One of the influential factors contributing to the teaching and learning process in the virtual classroom interaction is anxiety. Achievement and the successfulness in the classroom are also determined by anxiety. Some learners show their success depends upon their anxiety. During the processing stage, students' anxiety can influence both the fluency and the accuracy of speaking (Suleimenova, 2013).

In the world today, some research reports have been reported that the learning process in the classroom anxiety relating to students' socio-economic and family background, students' self-confidence, lecturers' role in the classroom setting, students' beliefs about materials, lecturers' arrogance in the teaching-learning process and other forms of anxiety which are frequently occurred in the classroom (Weda & Sakti, 2018). Studies on language anxiety have recently started to explore various traits relating to learners' anxiety in language learning, ranging from the relationship between students' anxiety and their academic achievement (Weda & Sakti, 2018). Since anxiety is vital in the learning and teaching process in the classroom presentation, some researchers have focused their study on this interesting topic (Weda & Sakti, 2018; Singh & Thukral, 2009; Horwitz, 2001; Shakir, 2014; Özüttürk & Hursen, 2013; Suleimenova, 2013; and Mak, 2011).

Trang, Moni & Baldauf (2012) state that there are various factors that might affect foreign language learning faced by learners when learning a foreign language, those factors are attitude, motivation, anxiety, and self-

efficacy beliefs. Of these affective factors, anxiety and self-efficacy beliefs have been given much attention by academics and researchers.

Self-efficacy refers to one's beliefs about accomplishing an individual task and can potentially affect choice of activities, effort, persistence, and learning outcome (Dale H. Schunk, 1995). Self-efficacy becomes very interesting topic in the learning process in the classroom setting and many researchers focus their study on this topic to explore the relationship of self-efficacy and learning outcome. Ghasemolanda and Hashim (2013) argue that the teachers' perceived self-efficacy was positively correlated with self-reported English proficiency.

Self-efficacy is one of influential factors in the learning process in the classroom and it becomes fundamental support to succeed in the learning achievement. Therefore, many researchers and academics pay their attention in this interesting topic in the learning process in the classroom setting (Mustafa, et al., 2022; Ghasemolanda & Hashim, 2013; Weda, et al., 2018, Sahril & Weda, 2018; Sulastriningsih, et al., 2019; Pajares, 2003; & Igbaria & Iivari, 1995).

With a focus on Indonesian Undergraduate Indonesian Language and Literature majors at the Faculty of Languages and Literature Universitas Negeri Makassar (UNM), this study aims to examine the effects of anxiety and self-efficacy on the students' virtual interaction in online learning.

Research Questions

The research questions underlying this present research are as follows:

1. Does anxiety influence virtual interaction in online learning?
2. Does self-efficacy influence virtual interaction in online learning?

Review of Literature

Anxiety

It is true to say that this digital age is so called an age of anxiety because every aspect of human life determined by extra effort to do it. The present age may be said to be an age of anxiety (Singh & Thukral, 2009). Singh & Thukral (2009) therefore argue that anxiety has been taken synonymous with apprehension, dread and uneasiness. This reaction or feeling stems from fear, but on the other hand, it is more a fear of what will occur or what has occurred than of a clearly apparent fear-provoking condition. Anxiety is a state of diffused worry and it is unclear, non-specific and objectless (Singh & Thukral, 2009). Anxiety is defined as suffering or uneasiness of the mind caused by dread of danger or bad luck (Suleimenova, 2013).

Anxiety is a popular term in the learning – teaching process at schools and universities. What is anxiety? There are lots of definitions about anxiety proposed by researchers and academics. Anxiety is a common emotion when dealing with daily stresses and problems (Chan, 2019). Anxiety is defined as fear, panic, and worry (Abu-Rabia, 2004 as cited in Weda & Sakti, 2018).

Numerous empirical studies have reported that anxiety has correlation and influence on academic achievement (Weda & Sakti, 2018, Singh & Thukral, 2009). Vitasari et al (2010) as cited in Weda and Sakti (2018) argue that anxiety is a specific-situation that refers to anxiety conditions that are practiced during study process and could be trouble of academic achievement. They then state that study anxiety has two important scopes which include physiological arousal and cognitive anxiety as revealed in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Theoretical model of study anxiety upon academic performance (Vitasari et al. as cited in Weda & Sakti, 2018).

Emotionally, anxiety refers to physiological reactions, such as blushing or racing heart, and behavioral responses, such as, stumbling and fiddling. Worry refers to cognitive responses, such as self-deprecating thoughts or task unrelated thoughts (Woodrow, 2006 as cited in Weda & Sakti, 2018).

Table 1. The Measurement of Anxiety in Previous Studies

Researcher	Research Site & Year	Instrument	Subjects/Participants
Sukardi Weda – Andi Elsa Fadhilah Sakti	Indonesia, 2018	The study anxiety level was measured using	A total 116 students, 96 females and 20 males

		Sangiry and Sail's Test Anxiety Measurement (TAM). Meanwhile, students' academic performance was measured using Grade Pont Average (GPA).	students participated in this study.
Sukardi Weda, Iskandar Abdul Samad, Andi Anto Patak, Siti Sarah Fitriani	Indonesia, 2018	Questionnaire	125 undergraduate students at English Department, Faculty of Languages and Literature State University of Makassar, Indonesia
Singh, S & Thukral, P	India, 2009	General anxiety scale for children (Sharma, 2003) has been used to measure the anxiety of the students.	Over a sample of 400 (200 boys and 200 girls) high school students studying in Xth class in 8 different schools (4 urban and 4 rural) affiliated to CBSE, New Delhi.
Elaine K. Horwitz	2001	An instrument, the Foreign Language Classroom Anxiety Scale (FLCAS), to measure this anxiety.	Students
Mohd. Shakir	2014	A reliable and valid, Academic Anxiety Scale standardized by Dr. A.K. Singh and Dr. A Sen Gupta was used to collect the data.	A sample of 352 students of senior secondary school was taken through random sampling technique.
Güliz Özütürk & Cigdem Hursen	Turkey, 2013	Questionnaire with a Likert scale is ranging from strongly disagree to strongly agree were used to collect data and demographic features of the participants	Turkey's university students.
ZiashSuleimenova	Kazakhstan, 2013	Interview and Questionnaire	Kazakh anxious language learners
Assyifa, Ayu MaulidiaHandayani, & Siska Rizkiani	Indonesia, 2019	Questionnaire and Interview	30 students from 465 students of first-grade students as the respondents of this research
Barley Mak	China, 2011	The research was carried out in three phases: the pilot, the quantitative phase (questionnaires) and the qualitative phase (semi-structured interviews, discussion and participant observation).	f a group of 313 Chinese ESL first-year university students in Hong Kong
Meihua Liu	China, 2006	Survey, observations, reflective journals and interviews	Chinese undergraduate non-English majors at three different proficiency levels.

Self-efficacy

It is vital to note that self-efficacy belief is a motivational construct in the learning process based upon self-perception of competence rather than actual level of competence (Ghasemboland, Farimah & Fatimah Binti Hashim, 2013).

Table 2. The Measurement of Self-efficacy in Previous Studies

Researcher	Research Site & Year	Instrument	Subjects/Participants
Faizal Mustafa, Sukardi Weda, TanzirMasykar	Indonesia, 2022	Questionnaire	
Farimah Ghasembolanda& Fatimah Binti Hashim	Middle-east country in Asia, 2013	Data were collected through a survey administered to 187 teachers.	Nonnative English speaking (NNES) EFL teachers in terms of personal capabilities to teach English as a Foreign Language (EFL) and their perceived English language proficiency in selected language centers in one Middle-East country.
Sukardi Weda, Iskandar Abdul Samad, Andi Anto Patak, Siti Sarah Fitriani	Indonesia, 2018	Questionnaire	One hundred and twenty-five undergraduate students of English Literature Study Program of Faculty of Languages and Literature Universitas Negeri Makassar and students of graduate program of English education (TEFL) participated in this study.
Sahril&Sukardi Weda	Indonesia, 2018	Questionnaire	50 students, 30 females and 20 males of English Department, Faculty of Languages and Literature Universitas Negeri Makassar
SulastriningsihDjumingin, Sukardi Weda, Juanda	Indonesia, 2019	Questionnaire	The participants of this study were the students of Indonesian Education and Literature Department, Faculty of Education and Literature, Universitas Negeri Makassar (N = 62). There were 55 or 88.71% females and 7 or 11.29% males from the seventh (42 or 67.75%) and ninth (20 or 32.25%) semesters
Frank Pajares	2003	-	A brief overview of Bandura's social cognitive theory and of self-efficacy is first provided, followed by a description of the manner in which writing self-efficacy beliefs are typically operationalized and assessed.
M Igbaria& Iivari	Finland, 1995	TAM (Technology Acceptance Model)	A survey of 450 microcomputer users in

			Finland found strong support for the conceptual model. I
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Virtual Interaction

Research Hypothesis

H0 = Anxiety does not influence virtual interaction.

H1 = Anxiety influences significantly virtual interaction.

Research Method

Participants

The participants of the present research were the students of Indonesian and Literature Study Program Faculty of Languages and Literature Universitas Negeri Makassar, Indonesia in 2023/2024 academic year.

Data Collection and Procedure

Questionnaires were sent to students participating in this study using Google Forms. Before participants opened the questionnaire link, they were asked to read carefully the participant's informed consent form which consisted of a description of the study, a description of the questionnaire, information about how the study results benefited the participants, confidential information, voluntary participation and withdrawal information, and contact of the researcher information. Therefore, the participants who agreed to participate in the study clicked on the link to access the questionnaire. It took about 11 to 15 minutes to complete the questionnaire.

Instrument

The measurements were questionnaires which aimed to investigate anxiety, self-efficacy, and virtual interaction, measured by Likert-scale of anxiety, self-efficacy, and virtual interaction. The questionnaires were written in Indonesian and the participants were asked to rate their perception on the anxiety, self-efficacy, and virtual interaction in online learning. In this study, the participants were asked to rate their perceptions with response to the questionnaires on a 5-point Likert-scale on which 5 = strongly agree, 4 = agree, 3 = neutral, 2 = disagree, and 1 = strongly disagree.

Data Analysis

This present research on the effect of anxiety and self-efficacy on virtual interaction in online learning is a quantitative research design was performed. In this study, the researchers employed inferential and descriptive statistics. Inferential statistics was applied to see the effect of anxiety on virtual interaction and the effect of self-efficacy on virtual interaction. Descriptive statistics which cover percentage, standard deviation (SD), and means were used to characterize the students' perceived levels of the variables tested.

Findings and Discussion

Firstly, the researchers will present the demographic information of participants in the questionnaire. Secondly, the researchers will present the descriptive and inferential statistics of the study.

Table 4. Demographic Information of Participants in Questionnaire

Demographic Information		Frequency	Percentage
Gender	Male	60	18.3
	Female	267	81.7
Age	17	1	0.3
	18	34	10.4
	19	104	31.8
	20	101	30.9
	21	53	16.2
	22	22	6.7
	23	5	1.5
	24	4	1.2
	25	1	0.3
	26	1	0.3
	27	1	0.3

Table 4 shows that there were 327 participants in the study. They were 60 or 18.3% males and 267 or 81.7% females. As revealed on the Table 4, the participants have a variety of ages, ranging from 17 to 41.

Descriptive Statistics

Table 5 illustrates the distribution of minimum, maximum, mean, and standard deviation (SD) for anxiety.

Table 5. Distributions of Participants' Responses on Anxiety

Item	Min	Max	Mean	SD
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1	1.00	5.0	2.68	0.980
2	1.00	5.0	3.26	1.035
3	1.00	5.0	3.76	0.897
4	1.00	5.0	3.58	1.021
5	1.00	5.0	3.37	0.833
6	1.00	5.0	2.99	0.998
7	1.00	5.0	3.22	1.006
8	1.00	5.0	3.14	1.015
9	1.00	5.0	2.56	0.963
10	1.00	5.0	3.10	1.007
11	1.00	5.0	3.30	1.084
12	1.00	5.0	3.97	0.968

Table 5 shows the participants' responses on the anxiety. The table 5 reveals that the minimum score was 1.00 of all items and the maximum score was 5.00 of all items. The standard deviation (SD) is also presented on the Table 5.

Table 6. The mean of each of the 12 items in Part One (Anxiety) of the questionnaire

Item No.	Statement	Mean	SD
1	I am not bothered by somebody speaking quickly in the virtual interaction in online class	2.68	0.980
2	I get upset when somebody speaks too quickly in the virtual interaction	3.26	1.035
3	I only feel comfortable during virtual interaction is when I have had a lot of time to prepare myself to study	3.76	0.897
4	I feel anxious if virtual class seems disorganized and unsystematic	3.58	1.021
5	I am self-confident in by ability to appreciate the meaning of dialogue in virtual class	3.37	0.833
6	I do not feel anxious when I hear unfamiliar words in virtual classroom	2.99	0.998
7	I never feel anxious when I have to explain materials in the virtual interaction the classroom presentation	3.22	1.006
8	I never feel nervous when I have to response the questions in the virtual interaction in online classroom	3.14	1.015
9	I get upset when I know how to express ideas, feelings, and thoughts in virtual interaction in the online class	2.56	0.963
10	I never get tense when I should present material in the virtual interaction	3.10	1.007
11	When I become anxious during a classroom presentation in virtual interaction, I cannot recall anything I studied before	3.30	1.084
12	I enjoy just listening to somebody expressing and sharing information in the virtual classroom	3.97	0.968

As revealed of the Table 6 that the rank mean score is item number 12 (I enjoy just listening to somebody expressing and sharing information in the virtual classroom) with mean 3.97. It is followed by the item number 4 (I feel anxious if virtual class seems disorganized and unsystematic) with mean 3.58. The minimum score is item number 9 (I get upset when I know how to express ideas, feelings, and thoughts in virtual interaction in the online class) with mean 2.56.

Table 7. illustrates the distribution of minimum, maximum, mean, and standard deviation (SD) for self-efficacy.
Table 7. Distributions of Participants' Responses on Self-efficacy

Item	Min	Max	Mean	SD
1	1.00	5.0	3.53	0.906
2	1.00	5.0	2.91	0.929
3	1.00	5.0	3.50	0.817
4	1.00	5.0	2.47	0.889
5	1.00	5.0	2.53	0.990
6	1.00	5.0	2.19	0.997
7	1.00	5.0	3.88	0.907
8	1.00	5.0	3.03	1.458
9	1.00	5.0	3.27	1.786
10	1.00	5.0	3.59	0.912

11	1.00	5.0	3.06	0.872
12	1.00	5.0	3.42	0.864

Descriptive statistics for the scale of participants' responses on self-efficacy is presented on the Table 7 which shows the minimum and maximum score of each item and the Table 7 also reveals the mean and standard deviation (SD) of the participants' responses on self-efficacy questionnaire.

Table 8. The mean of each of the 12 items in Part two (Self-efficacy) of the questionnaire

Item No.	Statement	Mean	SD
1	Even the learning topics is difficult in virtual interaction, I am sure that I can comprehend it and finish it	3.53	0.906
2	I am not confident in understanding difficult learning topics in virtual interaction	2.91	0.929
3	I am sure that I can do well the discussed topics in the virtual interaction	3.50	0.817
4	When the learning exercises in virtual classroom are too difficult, I always give up or only complete the easy parts	2.47	0.889
5	No matter how much effort I put in, I cannot learn a variety of topics in online classroom well	2.53	0.990
6	To finish the assignment in the virtual classroom, I frequently ask my classmates for the answers rather than thinking of by myself	2.19	0.997
7	I encourage myself to succeed in virtual classroom	3.88	0.907
8	When I identify the content or the material in the virtual interaction difficult, I used to ignore it	3.03	1.458
9	I try to learn all difficult topics in the online classroom and I am convinced to be successful	3.27	1.786
10	I believe that I can do all difficult tasks in the virtual classroom well	3.59	0.912
11	I sometimes cannot complete all difficult topics in the online classroom	3.06	0.872
12	Virtual interaction improves my participation and involvement in the online classroom	3.42	0.864

Table 8 presents the mean and standard deviation (SD) of all items in questionnaire. As revealed on the Table 8 that the highest mean is item number 7 (I encourage myself to succeed in virtual classroom) with mean 3.88. It is followed by item number 10 (I believe that I can do all difficult tasks in the virtual classroom well) with mean 3.59 and the minimum mean is item number 6 (To finish the assignment in the virtual classroom, I frequently ask my classmates for the answers rather than thinking of by myself) with mean 2.19.

Table 9 illustrates the distribution of minimum, maximum, mean, and standard deviation (SD) for virtual interaction.

Table 9. Distributions of Participants' Responses on virtual interaction

Item	Min	Max	Mean	SD
1	1.00	5.0	3.62	0.953
2	1.00	5.0	2.89	1.112
3	1.00	5.0	3.35	0.945
4	1.00	5.0	2.61	1.000
5	1.00	5.0	2.63	1.025
6	1.00	5.0	3.46	0.912
7	1.00	5.0	2.70	0.796
8	1.00	5.0	2.82	0.946
9	1.00	5.0	2.81	0.900
10	1.00	5.0	2.68	1.006
11	1.00	5.0	3.34	0.922
12	1.00	5.0	3.05	0.940

Descriptive statistics for the scale of participants' responses on virtual interaction is shown on the Table 9. The Table 9 shows the minimum mean score, the maximum mean score, and standard deviation (SD) of all items in the questionnaire.

Table 10. The mean of each of the 12 items in Part two (Virtual interaction) of the questionnaire

Item No.	Statement	Mean	SD
1	Interaction virtually is very interesting in the digital technology era	3.62	0.953
2	I recommend to employ virtual interaction for all subjects at the university	2.89	1.112

	level		
3	Virtual interaction offers various activities to enhance students' competence	3.35	0.945
4	Virtual interaction is not interesting in the learning process	2.61	1.000
5	Virtual interaction does not encourage students to share ideas, feelings, and thoughts to others	2.63	1.025
6	I am happy to express ideas, feelings, and thoughts in the virtual interaction	3.46	0.912
7	I cannot understand what other students present in the virtual interaction	2.70	0.796
8	Virtual interaction in the online learning is boring	2.82	0.946
9	The students cannot learn transferring values from teachers in the virtual classroom	2.81	0.900
10	There is no problem faced in the virtual interaction	2.68	1.006
11	Virtual interaction in the online classroom can stimulate students to prepare themselves well	3.34	0.922
12	Students can handle all obstacles occurred in the virtual classroom	3.05	0.940

The highest rank of the items in questionnaire is item number 1 (Interaction virtually is very interesting in the digital technology era) with mean 3.62. The second rank is item number 3 (Virtual interaction offers various activities to enhance students' competence) with mean 3.35. The lowest rank is item number 4 (Virtual interaction is not interesting in the learning process) with mean 2.61.

Hypothesis Testing

The Result of Regression Analysis of Anxiety with Virtual Interaction

Table 11. Model summary of the effect of anxiety on virtual interaction at higher education institution

Variables Entered/Removed^a

Model	Variables Entered	Variables Removed	Method
1	Anxiety ^b	.	Enter

a. Dependent Variable: Virtual Interaction

b. All requested variables entered.

Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.562 ^a	.315	.313	4.687

a. Predictors: (Constant), Anxiety

Source: Data Processing SPSS, 2023

Table 11 shows coefficient correlation value R is 0.562 coefficient determination R² is 0.315 as determination index, is the percentage contributes to the effect of anxiety (X) on virtual interaction at higher education institution(Y). R² is 0.315, shows that 31.5% of contribution of anxiety (X) on virtual interaction at higher education institution (Y), the rest 59.5% influenced by other factors. The effect of independent variable anxiety (predictor/X1) on the change of dependent variable, virtual interaction (criterion/Y) is 31.5%, and the rest 59.5% influenced by other variables.

Table 12. Regression coefficient and the result of t testing the effect of anxiety on virtual interaction

ANOVA^a

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	3289.422	1	3289.422	149.752	.000 ^b
	Residual	7138.890	325	21.966		
	Total	10428.312	326			

a. Dependent Variable: Virtual Interaction

b. Predictors: (Constant), Anxiety

Coefficients^a

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	15.059	1.727		8.719	.000
	Anxiety	.431	.035	.562	12.237	.000

a. Dependent Variable: Virtual Interaction

Source: Data Processing SPSS, 2023

From table 12, regression coefficient (B), it is shown according to the following regression equation.

$$Y = 15.059 + 0.431X_1$$

This regression equation can be used to predict how independent variable influence dependent variable does. β_0 is Constanta value that shows that if there is no anxiety, virtual interaction is 15.059 unit. This means that if assumed that if there is no anxiety variable, virtual interaction as dependent variable is 15.059 unit. 0.431X₁ is regression coefficient that shows each addition of anxiety for 1 unit, so there will be virtual interaction 0.431 unit of anxiety.

The Result of Regression Analysis of Self-efficacy and Virtual Interaction

Table 13. Model summary of the effect of self-efficacy on virtual interaction at higher education institution

Variables Entered/Removed^a

Model	Variables Entered	Variables Removed	Method
1	Self Efficacy ^b	.	Enter

a. Dependent Variable: Virtual Interaction

b. All requested variables entered.

Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.635 ^a	.404	.402	4.374

a. Predictors: (Constant), Self Efficacy

Source: Data Processing SPSS, 2023

Table 12 shows coefficient correlation value R is 0.635 coefficient determination R² is 0.404 as determination index, is the percentage contributes to the effect of self-efficacy (X) on virtual interaction at higher education

institution (Y). R^2 is 0.404, shows that 40.4% of contribution of self-efficacy (X) on virtual interaction at higher education institution (Y), the rest 50.6% influenced by other factors. The effect of independent variable anxiety (predictor/X1) on the change of dependent variable, virtual interaction (criterion/Y) is 31.5%, and the rest 50.6% influenced by other variables.

14. Regression coefficient and the result of t testing the effect of self-efficacy on virtual interaction

ANOVA^a

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	4211.044	1	4211.044	220.127	.000 ^b
	Residual	6217.268	325	19.130		
	Total	10428.312	326			

a. Dependent Variable: Virtual Interaction

b. Predictors: (Constant), Self Efficacy

Coefficients^a

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	13.490	1.533		8.798	.000
	Self Efficacy	.601	.041	.635	14.837	.000

a. Dependent Variable: Virtual Interaction

Source: Data Processing SPSS, 2023

From table 12, regression coefficient (B), it is shown according to the following regression equation.

$$Y = 13.490 + 0.601X_1$$

This regression equation can be used to predict how independent variable influence dependent variable does. β_0 is Constanta value that shows that if there is no self-efficacy, virtual interaction is 13.490 unit. This means that if assumed that if there is no self-efficacy variable, virtual interaction as dependent variable is 13.490 unit. $0.601X_1$ is regression coefficient that shows each addition of self-efficacy for 1 unit, so there will be virtual interaction 0.601 unit of self-efficacy.

Discussion

This present study rejects the study of Horwitz (2001) who argues that not only is it intuitive to many people that anxiety negatively influences language learning, it is logical because anxiety has been found to interfere with many types of learning and has been one of the most highly examined variables in all of psychology and education. Horwitz (2001) therefore adds that there have been a number of studies in a number of instructional contexts with varying target languages which find a negative relationship between specific measures of language anxiety and language achievement. This present study also disagrees with the study from Shakir (2014) who claims that academic anxiety decreases students' learning capabilities and hinders excellent academic performance. Weda et al (2018) argued that there was a significant correlation of high-level anxiety and low academic performances among English students at English Department of Faculty of Languages and Literature State University of Makassar, Indonesia.

The result of the study indicates that there is a positive effect of anxiety on virtual interaction at Indonesian Education and Literature Department, Faculty of Languages and Literature State University of Makassar, Makassar Indonesia with significant effect with ($p=0.00$). This study agrees with the study by Suleimenova (2013) who argued that during the processing stage, students' anxiety can influence both the fluency and the accuracy of speaking.

Another finding of the study is that there is a significant effect of self-efficacy on virtual interaction at Indonesian Education and Literature Department, Faculty of Languages and Literature State University of Makassar, Makassar Indonesia with significant effect with ($p=0.00$). This study agrees with the study conducted by Ghasemband, Farimah and Fatimah Binti Hashim (2013) who claimed that it is vital to note that self-efficacy belief is a motivational construct in the learning process based upon self-perception of competence rather than actual level of competence.

Conclusion

There are some important implications derived from this present study, those are as follows:

Firstly, as revealed in the findings and the discussion section of the study, that the rank mean score is item number 12 (I enjoy just listening to somebody expressing and sharing information in the virtual classroom) with

mean 3.97. This means that the students are happy to share ideas, thoughts, and feeling in the online learning with their mates. It is followed by the item number 4 (I feel anxious if virtual class seems disorganized and unsystematic) with mean 3.58. This symbolizes that the students are anxious if the teacher in the online classroom do not organize and manage the virtual classroom well.

Secondly, the result of the study reveals that the mean and standard deviation (SD) of all items in questionnaire. The result shows that the highest mean is item number 7 (I encourage myself to succeed in virtual classroom) with mean 3.88. It is followed by item number 10 (I believe that I can do all difficult tasks in the virtual classroom well) with mean 3.59. This indicates that the students motivate themselves to be successful in the online classroom and they believe to complete all difficult tasks in the online classroom.

Finally, this study also explores the effect of anxiety and self-efficacy on virtual interaction at higher education institution in Indonesia, that is the students at Indonesian Language and Literature Department, Faculty of Languages and Literature State University of Makassar, Indonesia. The result of the study indicates that there is a significant effect of anxiety on virtual interaction at Indonesian Education and Literature Department, Faculty of Languages and Literature State University of Makassar, Makassar Indonesia with significant effect with ($p=0.00$).

The result of the study also indicates that there is a significant effect of self-efficacy on virtual interaction at Indonesian Education and Literature Department, Faculty of Languages and Literature State University of Makassar, Makassar Indonesia with significant effect with ($p=0.00$).

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